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Abstract title: Field investigations on exposure reduction by green infrastructures in near-road environments: the Guildford iSCAPE case study

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Abstract text

As a part of an ongoing EU-funded project iSCAPE (www.iscapeproject.eu), this study aims to quantify the impact of green barriers under a variety of real-world conditions through field measurements in Guildford, a typical UK town close to London. We studied effects of green infrastructure (GI) on the concentrations of particulate matter $\leq 10 \mu\text{m}$ (PM_{10}), $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$), $\leq 1 \mu\text{m}$ (PM_1), black carbon (BC) and particle number concentrations (PNC) under three GI configurations – (i) hedges only, (ii) trees only, and (iii) a mix of trees and hedges/shrubs – separately in close ($<1\text{m}$) and away ($>2\text{m}$) road conditions. The changes in concentrations of PM_{10} , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, PM_1 , BC and PNC at all these six sites were estimated by comparing simultaneous measurements behind and in-front/clear area of GI. The largest reductions were consistently recorded for mix of trees and hedges sites in near-road conditions and hedge only site in away-road conditions. Analysis of effects of wind direction on pollution levels showed highest reduction during winds parallel to the road. The evaluation of various fractions of PM displayed that hedge only and combination of trees and hedges lowered fine particles behind GI. The SEM-EDS analysis indicated dominance of natural particles and reduction in vehicle-related particles (i.e., iron and its oxides, Ba, Cr, Mn) behind GI compared to in-front/clear area. This work provides evidences for air quality modifications of different GI configurations

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on multiple pollutants in near road environments. Moreover this works helps in developing guidelines for GI design to reduce air pollution exposure near busy roads.

Motivation

Most of the urban population live, work and spend most of their day near road environment, where pollutant concentrations remains higher. Exposure to these higher concentration levels may lead to wide range of health implications such as exacerbation of asthma, impaired lung function, cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Green interventions such as vegetation barriers, trees, hedges and green walls are effective in reducing pollutant concentration near open road regions by up to 60% than a clear area without the vegetation (Abhijith et al., 2017). This work evaluates air pollution reduction potentials of various GI in near-road environments, with an aim to provide practical recommendations on GI configurations to reduce exposure levels in near-road environments.

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References

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